

Research

How China's Belt and Road Initiative Implements in Vietnam and What Risk Factors Affect Vietnam-China Cooperation

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Abstract: This study analyzes how the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) implements in Vietnam by focusing on the five "connectivities" of policy coordination, infrastructure connectivity, trade connectivity, financial integration, and people-to-people connection. The BRI has witnessed pragmatic achievements over its six years of implementation and has strengthened potential trading and investment activities between the aforementioned countries. However, this study focuses on the basis of Vietnam's hesitation due to existing and potential risks from the BRI (i.e., debt risks, governance risks, stranded infrastructure, environmental risks, and geopolitical and security risks). Thus, our study provides a solid contribution to policymakers' understanding of the factors that affect two countries' cooperation and the continuing efforts of policy implementation for enhanced connectivity. Overall, the study suggests a comprehensive policy improvement to minimize the risks for participating countries and help attain better cooperation in terms of sustainability

Keywords: The Belt and Road Initiative; Implications; Risk-factors; Vietnam-China Cooperation.

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Introduction

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has made remarkable achievements since China's President Xi Jinping carried it out in late 2013. So far, China has signed 174 BRI collaboration agreements with 126 countries and 29 international organizations (Moody Andrew, 2019; Xinhua, 2019). Recently, China has been expanding the scope of the Initiative to areas further away: towards parts of Africa, Latin America, South Pacific, etc. Africa is currently the continent with the largest number of participating partners in the BRI (37 countries) as compared to Asia (36 countries). Through the BRI, China has made attempts to build a global trade and infrastructure network inclusive of roads, railways, seaports,

airports, pipelines, and fiber optic cables. The BRI will envelop about 64 percent of the earth's population and over 30 percent of world GDP (Huang, 2016).

In the context of the BRI as an important source of funding, Vietnam may want to tap into it so as to finance Vietnam's infrastructure development projects. Although previous studies mainly focus on BRI: background, motivation, framework, opportunities to intensify regional and global trade relations (Huang, 2016; Yu, 2017; Yu et al., 2019), as well as BRI implications and challenges in Asian economies and Africa in general (Ba, 2019; Chung, 2018; Liu & Lim, 2019; Shariatnia & Azizi, 2017); few studies explain why Vietnam still remains largely ambivalent and hesitant towards China's strategic Initiative (Hiep, 2018; Thuan, 2017). Therefore, this study attempts to answer these three key questions: (1) How is the BRI being implemented in Vietnam?, (2) What risk factors are affecting Vietnam-China cooperation in the framework of the five major connectivities? and (3) How are the risks minimized in order to help the two countries cooperate in terms of sustainability in future?

In order to answer these three questions, this study first presents the BRI implications for Vietnam within the context of five major connectivities of policy coordination, infrastructure connectivity, trade connectivity, financial integration, and people-to-people connection (The State Council, 2015; Xinhua, 2017). Second, the study sheds light on Vietnam's hesitation by presenting their perspective towards the major risks for many large infrastructure projects implemented in BRI countries, such as debt risks, governance risks, stranded infrastructure, environmental risks (Vu, Cu, Min, & Wang, 2017; World Bank, 2019), and geopolitical and security risks (Soong & Nguyen, 2018; Thai, 2018).

Third, this study will contribute to the minimization of environmental and corruption risks, expand trade, increase transparency, and improve collaborative sustainability through five comprehensive policies (i.e., transparency policies, anti-corruption policies, environmental sustainability policies, financial policies, and balancing policies) for China and Vietnam. Finally, this study offers significant implications for academics, local business people, and policymakers to capitalize on the positive effects of BRI infrastructure projects and make sure that the benefits are mutually shared.

2. BRI implications

2.1. Policy coordination

First, from 2013 to present, several Chinese high-level leaders have visited Vietnam, including General Secretary, President Xi Jinping (November 2015, November 2017), Prime Minister Li Keqiang (October 2013), Vice Premier Zhang Gaoli (July 2015), Vice Premier Hu Chunhua (September 2018), Chairman of the National People's Congress Standing Committee Zhang Dejiang (November 2016), Chairman of the National Committee of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference (CPPCC) Yu Zhengsheng (December 2014), State Councillor and Foreign Minister Wang Yi (March 2018). The visit to Vietnam by General Secretary and President of China Xi Jinping (November 2017) was the first overseas visit of the Party of China's highest leader right after the 19th National Congress.

Second, from 2013 to the present, senior Vietnamese leaders have conducted eleven diplomatic exchanges and have attended international activities in China. Including General Secretary Nguyen Phu Trong twice (April 2015, January 2017), President Tran Dai Quang once (May 2017), Prime Minister Nguyen Xuan Phuc twice (September 2016, April 2019), President Truong Tan Sang thrice (June 2013, November 2014, September 2015), Prime Minister Nguyen Tan Dung once (September 2013) and National Assembly Chairman Nguyen Sinh Hung once (December 2015), National Assembly Chairman Nguyen Thi Kim Ngan once (July 2019). All the above diplomatic exchanges were made to work on the policy coordination.

Third, Vietnam signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) during China's President Xi Jinping's visit to Hanoi in November 2017, boosting the connectivity between the "Two Corridors and One Economic Circle" (TCOEC) plan and the BRI. However, the TCOEC plan formation was not conducted until 2013, when the BRI was launched. According to Vietnamese scholar Le Hong Hiep, the MoU signing does not imply that the BRI will see breakthroughs in Vietnam in the near future, and Vietnam still maintains control over the TCOEC plan (Hiep, 2018). Besides, Vietnam does not

want the TCOEC plan to be treated as a part of the BRI. Moreover, Vietnam is generally well aware of the BRI that can help countries along the route achieve higher infrastructure connectivity levels, yet cautious about the Initiative's implications for its nation. Presently, Vietnam is still waiting for the practical outcomes of the first batch of the BRI projects before making any further decisions. Similarly, some countries in the region and other continents decided to take a wait-and-see approach if the cooperation can bring actual benefits from working with China's BRI (Shean, 2018). Last but not least, Vietnamese Prime Minister Nguyen Xuan Phuc attended the second Belt and Road Forum in Beijing in April 2019. During this event, China's President Xi stressed that the two sides should align the BRI with the TCOEC plan. Speaking at the Forum, Mr. Phuc emphasized that cooperation within the Initiative must be based on equality, transparency, openness, and sincerity, ensuring sustainability, effectiveness, inclusiveness, and mutually beneficial and respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, international law. From the foundation of development, Vietnam is willing to cooperate with China to enhance their bilateral ties and strategic partnership for both countries' mutual benefit and bring regional peace and prosperity.

2.2. Infrastructure connectivity

From China's perspective, under the TCOEC plan, many projects have been conducted. However, from Vietnam's perspective, there are no new infrastructural projects in Vietnam that can be officially associated with BRI funding. The exception of Hanoi's urban railway, Cat Linh-Ha Dong has received USD250 million from the BRI project. Although the loan was released in 2017, it is not officially recognized as a BRI investment project by both sides. At the moment, there are no other infrastructure projects associated with BRI investment.

2.3. Trade connectivity

In 2014, the Vietnam-China trade grew exponentially and accounted for more than 17.4% of total China-ASEAN trade in 2014 (Tong & Xin, 2015). According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of China, the total bilateral trade revenue between China and Vietnam in 2015 was USD 95.848 billion, representing a year-on-year increase of 14.6%. Among them, China's exports to Vietnam were USD 66.017 billion, an increase of 3.8%, and imports from Vietnam were USD 29.831 billion, an increase of 49.1% from 2014 (National Data, 2020). China remains Vietnam's biggest trading partner for 12 consecutive years, and Vietnam is China's second-largest trading partner in Southeast Asia after Malaysia. In 2017, the total bilateral trade revenue between China and Vietnam exceeded the historical mark of USD 100 billion, reaching USD 121.99 billion, and marked an annual increase of 23.5%. Vietnam surpassed Malaysia to become China's largest ASEAN trading partner, with two-way trade hitting over USD10 billion for every month of 2018 (see Fig.1). Commodities of trade between Vietnam and China are various. Vietnam primarily exports agricultural and forestry products, processed and industrial products, and raw materials to China. Besides, Vietnam's major import products include equipment, materials for production, consumer goods, vehicles, electronic products, from China food.

Nevertheless, in the first quarter of 2019, China became Vietnam's largest investor with a newly registered capital of USD 3.82 billion, an increase of 80.1% from 2018. Additionally, the two countries' leadership has gained a shared understanding of strengthening their coordination and applying adequate measures to promote cooperation in economics and trade, production and investment capacity, infrastructure, financial integration healthily and sustainably. Significantly, the two sides set up a task force on infrastructure and monetary cooperation in April 2015 to promote trade. In September 2016, Vietnam and China signed an agreement to extend and supplement the development plan for 5-year economic and trade cooperation from 2017 to 2021. The Border Trade Agreement and many Memorandums of Understanding on joint planning were also revised.

In 2019, China's currency depreciated to the lowest exchange rate in the last 11 years. The People's Bank of China connected the devaluation of the Yuan to the new US tariff threat. The escalating tension between these two world powers has a significant impact on Vietnam's trade for 2019. On the one hand, there is an increase in purchasing China's goods from Vietnam and elsewhere. In figure 1, China's export to Vietnam raised to USD 97.868 billion in 2019. On the other hand, Vietnam's production and commerce activities of domestic enterprises would be harmfully affected.

Because Chinese products turn into cheaper, manufacturers of Vietnam will struggle in both domestic and international markets. Vietnamese economist Vu Dinh Anh informed domestic products would be hard to fight against cheap Chinese products in the local market. As a result, Vietnamese manufacturers would find it difficult to export their products to China and other markets due to higher prices compared to similar products originating from China (Nguyen, 2015).

Fig. 1. Vietnam-China Trade Value from 2013 to 2019

Data source: National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of China (National Data, 2020)

2.4. Financial integration

In fact, the China-Vietnam financial connection has made optimistic progress for Vietnam’s industrialization and economic and social development. Two countries announced the formal establishment of infrastructure and a financial and monetary cooperation working group. At present, there are three main financial platforms. One such platform is the Asia Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), which has headquarters in Beijing. AIIB is an initiative of Chinese President Xi at the APEC Summit in October 2013 with shared capital of USD100 billion. China has the largest voting share of 26.6% and holds veto power in AIIB major decisions requiring over 75% supermajority. The AIIB’s main goal is to invest in regional sustainable development by funding Asian infrastructure projects in five realms: rural development, urban development, transportation, energy, and logistic (Gabusi, 2017). In 2015, Vietnam signed the AIIB agreement in Beijing as a founding member. In 2017, AIIB President Jin Liqun re-affirmed that the AIIB will offer preferential credit to Vietnam to improve Vietnam's infrastructure and promise to provide various credit payments to private enterprises in Vietnam.

China Development Bank (CDB), Export and Import Bank of China (China Exim Bank) are also playing critical roles in the BRI fund. These two main international funding agencies fund USD334 billion of infrastructure projects globally, currently in various stages of implementation and execution (Business Wire, 2019). At the 2017 BRI Forum in Beijing, President Xi Jinping further encouraged investments by establishing special lending schemes for the CDB RMB250 billion (USD36 billion) and the Exim Bank RMB130 billion (USD19 billion, for a total of RMB380 billion (USD55 billion). Notably, China Exim Bank offered two kinds of preferential loans: concessional loans and preferential export buyer’s credit, involving power, energy, manufacturing, infrastructure, and other fields. These loans support the Chinese government in assisting developing countries, including Vietnam, to build their economies and accelerate industrialization. For example, on May 11, 2017, Hu Xiaolian, Chairman of the China Exim Bank, and Deputy Minister

of Finance of Vietnam Vu Thi Mai, signed an agreement on preferential foreign aid loans for Hanoi's urban railway Cat Linh- Ha Dong in Vietnam.

Finally, China's foreign policy lending banks remain active in the BRI. However, Vietnam has hesitation toward China's financial support because Chinese loans attract interest rates of 3 percent per year, higher than that of Japan (0.4 -1.2 percent), South Korea (0 -2 percent), or India (1.75 percent) (Tran, 2019). Besides, some Vietnamese analysts highlighted preferential credit loans from China are similar to export credit, which are conditional loans referring to the use of Chinese contractors (Chaudhury, 2018), and Vietnam has a redundant record with poor Chinese contractors (Hiep, 2018). Moreover, Chinese loans are subject to a 0.5 percent commitment fee and 0.5 percent administrative fee. In contrast, the loan's duration and grace period are shorter than those of other donors, standing at 15 years and five years, respectively. Therefore, China loans are less attractive compared to other donors. In 2016, Vietnam refused China Eximbank's USD 300 million credit to finance Van Don-Mong Cai Expressway project because it was less concessional than other ODA loans. In this sense, Vietnam carefully selects the aids to ensure capital recovery and debt repayment for its consideration and decision.

2.5. People-to-people connection

The two countries are cooperating in culture and sports by actively crafting a plan for implementation of the Vietnam-China cultural agreement for the period between 2013 and 2015 to strengthen cooperation in cultural production and human resources. Every year, the two sides exchanged many art troupes, cultural and sports exchanges, contributing to the enhanced friendship between people of both nations. The two sides have also effectively implemented the agreement on sports cooperation, and China helps Vietnam in training talented athletes. Moreover, China and Vietnam signed an agreement on establishing the first Confucius Institute at Hanoi University in 2013 (Hanban News, 2013), becoming an essential basis to promote educational and cultural relations. In 2017, a Chinese cultural center in Hanoi organized a range of cultural activities regarding art performances, cultural exhibitions, academic seminars, and cultural experiences. In 2018, 11,299 Vietnamese students studied in China through various types of scholarships, exchange programs, and other supported sources (Ministry of Education, 2019). Thus, the two countries reached comprehensive practical cooperation to promote further the extensive development of academic, sport, cultural interactions, and traditional friendship between Chinese and Vietnamese people.

Second, China and Vietnam signed a tourism cooperation plan for the period 2017-2019, which provided a strong impetus for the deep tourism cooperation between the two nations. The number of Chinese tourists has bumped up in recent years and always ranked first in the international tourist market to Vietnam. In 2017, the figure for Chinese tourists visiting Vietnam reached 4 million. In 2018, Vietnam received nearly 5 million Chinese visitors, up 23.9 percent compared to 2017, while China welcomed 6.3 million Vietnamese visitors to China, a double the figure in 2016 (3.2 million), making Vietnam the second largest tourist resource for Chinese tourism after Myanmar. Third, during the visit of Vietnam's General Secretary Nguyen Phu Trong in January 2017, Vietnam and China signed documents for cooperation in public health assistance between Vietnam Red Cross Association and China Red Cross. Overall, cross-country tourism and medical care are also necessary means for enhancing mutual understanding and trust between people in both nations and also are the foundation for the success of the Initiative.

3. Risks from BRI

3.1 Debt risks

Vietnam's demand for infrastructure investments is quite huge because of limited capital resources. According to the Global Infrastructure Outlook, Vietnam will require USD 605 billion for infrastructure development between 2016 and 2040. However, Vietnam has USD 503 billion, and a considerable gap is USD 102 billion (Global Infrastructure Outlook,

2017). In other words, Vietnam will have to proactively seek external sources of capital assistance to cover the funding gap, and BRI is an important financial source that Vietnam can tap into.

Even though Vietnam may consider tapping into China's BRI as a source of financial support, the country is well conscious of what happened to Thailand in 2016. First, the Thai government decided to give up China's loan to build a high-speed rail line linking Bangkok to the regional hub of Nakhon Ratchasima due to too high-interest rates (Global Times, 2016; Hiep, 2018). Second, in Sri Lanka, the government has struggled to repay its debt to Chinese firms; the nation officially handed over Hambantota's southern port to China on a 99-year lease (Schultz, 2017). As a result, China takes ownership and controls the equity stake. Third, an example of Malaysia, after Prime Minister Mahathir Mohamad came to power and immediately canceled the BRI projects worth USD 23 billion, accepting compensation, for reasons "beyond the Government's financial capacity" (Liu & Lim, 2019). Thus, these cases caution the risk of a "debt trap" from China in other countries' eyes, including Vietnam.

3.2 Governance risks

The most eminent governance risk in BRI projects has been identified as corruption. Vietnam is a developing country with a market-oriented economic regime with retaining government controls. At different levels, the state maintains controls key resources, grant licenses, permits, approves projects, grants subsidies, allow tax arrears, and offer access to infrastructure. Hence, corruption is such a headache issue of governance risks in Vietnam. In 2018, the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) by Transparency International showed that Vietnam ranked 117th among 180 countries and territories, plummeting by ten places compared to 2017. Besides, based on a 2018 survey implemented by the Mekong Development Research Institute in Vietnam, corruption is one of Vietnam's third top concerns.

On the same line of thought, Malaysia's corruption can be taken as a case study. The former Prime Minister Najib Razak was accused of corruption related to the BRI project. He was charged in court on four counts of corruption, a stunning fall from grace for the leader charged with extensive misappropriation of a state fund which he controlled. Also, in Kyrgyzstan, two former prime ministers Sapar Isakov and Jantoro Satybaldiev were arrested and jailed as the government-linked them to corruption cases in connection to a 2013 financial funding package from China, which included the modernization of the Bishkek Heating and Power Plant (Agata & Georgi, 2019). Thus, emerging governance cases in the BRI are very rampant in Asian countries, especially Vietnam. These cases highlighted the potential hazards of China's ambitious BRI.

3.3 Stranded infrastructure

In previous studies, Vietnam's researchers expressed concern about pointing out the stagnant progress of many Chinese-invested projects in Vietnam, including Hanoi's urban railway Cat Linh-Ha Dong project, the Da River Pipeline project in Hanoi, or the Thai Nguyen Steel Plant-Phase 2 project in Thai Nguyen Province.

The most glaring case is the Cat Linh-Ha Dong project in Hanoi, whose delay has been accounted for by the long-delayed railway and incurred a cost overrun of USD 316 million to USD 868 million. The project was supposed to operate by 2014, yet by the end of 2020, the project was still not yet completed. Dr. Le, a renowned Vietnamese economist, advised the government to reconsider the legislation on investments and tenders. He pointed out that because Vietnam's Bidding Law gives priority to the lowest bidder, Chinese contractors often bid at very low prices, so they always win the bids. After they win, they extend the construction period's time and increase the cost and prices times the original price (Tran, 2019).

The government of Vietnam is also concerned about the quality of the construction materials supplied by Chinese contractors. In March 2016, a similar case of Vinaconex Water Supply Joint Stock Company (Viwasupco) considered to invest in Da River Project-Phase II and announced Xinxing Pipeline-maker Corporation from China won the contract after bidding 11.8% less than the investor's required price. However, the pipelines were supplied by the first phase Chinese contractor have ruptured 18 times due to the poor quality of the iron pipelines used for the project. After investigation, Vietnam's government requested to postpone signing the contract with Xinxing and address the

underlying problems. Repair work spends over USD 731,000, and approximately 200,000 families, hospitals, and other public areas in Hanoi were influenced by water cutting for 386 hours. Finally, this sparked protests from the locals due to the contractor's Chinese pipes' low quality.

Another case is Thai Nguyen steel plant-phase 2. The contractor China Metallurgical Group Corporation (MCC) was appointed engineering, procurement, and construction (EPC) contractor in 2007 and was given 30 months to complete it. As of today, the project is still stalled. The investment capital had been raised from VND3.8 trillion (USD170.4 million) to VND 8 trillion (USD361.4 million) in 2009. In June 2012, the contractors abandoned the contract leaving behind a stalled project. In sum, China typically requests conditions on their preferential loans, including the use of Chinese contractors, technologies, and machinery. Yet, Vietnam has abundant experience with Chinese contractors' low record and quality construction in many Vietnam projects.

3.4 Environmental risks

In recent studies, many scientists and environmentalists have studied BRI's negative effects on the surrounding physical environment. China's ambitious project promotes large-scale infrastructure, and if those activities are not handled carefully by the two sides, permanent environmental damage is apparent.

First, the Chinese government has encouraged Chinese businesses to invest abroad in the past four years and solve the Chinese manufacturing surplus problem. However, Vietnam has warned that those Chinese surplus products and obsolete equipment, and environmentally polluting

equipment, and environmentally polluting technologies, are sent to other countries under Chinese investments will further complicate the challenges (Thuan, 2017). In this vein, Vietnam is anticipated to face environmental consequences in the future due to the high redundancy in manufacturing capacity provided by China's contractors.

Second, according to Samithi Sok, there are environmental concerns in Cambodia on the massive BRI's projects' adverse ecological effects, causing a high deforestation rate. The forest cover decreased from 70% of the rainforest area in 1970 to 3.1% in 2014. A new border belt and road connecting Cambodia with Vietnam is currently under construction and will cut through Virachey National Park - a vast area of mountainous forests, highland prairies, and deep river canyon, spanning 3,325 square kilometers (Sok, 2017). In this sense, BRI infrastructural projects can lead to pollution, the spread of invasive species, restrict animal movement, loss of habitat, and wildlife's death, and affect ecosystems.

Third, Myanmar's Irrawaddy River, Myitsone Dam project was suspended due to concerns about the dam's interference with the local environment. The dam constructed by the Chinese has adversely interfered with the environment. Significantly, Dr. Myint Zaw, a renowned environmentalist, warned that the dam would most likely diminish the river hence wipes out the forest that holds rich biodiversity (BBC News, 2019). Thus, the Government of Vietnam and other countries are concerned about the environmental impacts of land use, forests, biodiversity, water use, and other natural resources in all participating economies.

3.5 Geopolitical and security risks

Most of the prior studies view the BRI links with China's foreign policy and is interpreted as an economic development strategy. According to prof. Shi Yinhong, China's foreign policy moved away from hard power and strategic military influence to adopt soft power and strategic economic tools (Shi, 2015). The BRI aims at building a strategic geoeconomic with a clear demonstration of the phrase made by Chinese President Xi that Asians should spearhead Asian affairs. Besides, other researchers showed that the BRI is related to the growth of both geopolitical and geoeconomic affairs regionally and globally to compete with the United States (Blanchard, 2018; Blanchard & Flint, 2017; Flint & Zhu, 2018). Flint and Zhu (2018) show that forming relationships through economic connections will have intended and unforeseen geopolitical consequences and strategic calculations with political-military goals and consequences.

From a security perspective, the China-Vietnam dispute on maritime demarcations has put Vietnam sovereignty at stake in recent years. Vietnamese have shown a lot of patriotism for their country and have defended their land continuously against the Chinese invasion in the South China Sea. This state of affairs has been detrimental to trade and

economic integration. Conversely, given such security concerns to Chinese workers in Pakistan and Sri Lanka, China built China’s naval bases at Gwadar and Hambantota Ports to protect Chinese workers. These Chinese military stations will raise security issues of sovereignty in hosting countries. In this vein, Vietnam is still skeptical about joining the BRI because it wants to safeguard its geopolitical framework. The BRI is designed to covers shipping and land routes in various countries. Therefore, The BRI is viewed to bring uncertain vulnerability from geographical connectivity, poses political, credit, and security risks.

4. Managing the risks

4.1 Transparency policies

Regarding transparency policies, China should offer more public information on project plans, financial and budgetary costs, and procurement to enhance the efficiency of infrastructure funds and operations and national development strategy. Building better transparency is a crucial action to support community participation and build public confidence in investment decisions. According to Zoran Radosavljevic, the Mission of China and the EU indicated that they had scanty knowledge about any particular projects. They further cautioned that governments should ask companies to strictly follow related laws and regulations in project bidding, tendering, construction, and operation (Agata & Georgi, 2019).

After the second BRI Forum, China’s policy on transparency improved. Besides, China has enacted relevant laws coupled with other regulatory documents to manage bilateral ties. The Chinese government is keen on key BRI projects to promote a clean business environment. Overall, the investors that fail to comply with this should be blacklisted.

4.2 Anti-corruption policies

In order to eliminate corruption in the infrastructure sector, this study suggests that the government can adopt anti-corruption policies by initiating monitoring and measures that include audits (Liu & Lin, 2012), construction sector transparency initiative (CoST) (Krishnan, 2009), red flags (Ferwerda, Deleanu, & Unger, 2017; Tackett, 2010), integrity pacts, information power, community monitoring, and citizen report system. The function of each policy is as shown in the table follow.

Table 1. Functions of anti-corruption policies

Policy	Function
Auditing	To check on accountability and abuse of office and resources.
Construction Sector Transparency Initiative (CoST)	CoST works globally with governments, sectors, and civil society to improve value investment and anti-corruption organizations by increasing public infrastructure transparency and accountability.
Red Flags (RF)	RF are widely used to reduce the risk of corruption in public procurement. Some warning indicators alert the officials on a likely case of corruption in the construction project implementation cycle. Not necessarily a sign of fraud, the warning encourages officials to identify and monitor additional areas of potential vulnerability.
Integrity Pacts (IP)	IP is an agreement to limit acts of corruption between the government and investors and penalize non-compliance in the bidding and the execution of

	the contract. BRI economies can rely on these regulations to check on the heads of procurement and prospective contractors' conduct.
Information and Communications Technology Tools	Vietnam may utilize internet-based solutions, online procurement, procurement supervision, and autonomous purchasing agents to enhance the level of transparency in projects. Property, cost, and performance information give proof of accountability and transparency. Tools like e-procurement can help achieve procurement efficiency and manage contracts. The main advantage of the online system is the free availability of information to any interested party.
Community Oversight (CO)	CO is based on the fact that non-state actors can publicly perform their duties, improve governance, decrease effectiveness, and fight corruption. Vietnam can use it at specific stages of the project cycle to reduce liability.
Citizen Reporting System	Report cards can enhance project management by providing systematic feedback from public service users. They can offer communities, civil society organizations, and local governments a rigorous and positive agenda for dialogue with infrastructure providers to improve improvement projects and reduce corruption.

Source: Compiled by the author

4.3 Environmental policies

Due to the environmental damage and resource-wasting along with parts of the BRI's projects, this study suggests China adopts China's Circular Economy, which has been implemented in China since 2002. The Circular Economy is an environmentally sustainable policy that can manage China's resources, reduce raw material exploitation, and safeguard natural resources while integrating economic growth and sustainability practices in future decades (Ali, Kennedy, Kiesecker, & Geng, 2018). We suggest that the BRI infrastructure projects adhere to China's environmental regulations like China's standards at its home now.

Also, the Strategic Environmental and Social Assessments (SESAs) are needed for the BRI. SESAs systematically evaluate the environmental consequences of policies and projects proposed. SESAs ensure that these projects are resolved appropriately at the earliest stages of decision-making. Besides, Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) can collect information about the environmental impact of actual projects before organizations decide whether to carry projects out. EIAs can avoid irreparable damage and create substantial preservation and social benefits, such as biodiversity safeguard, carbon storeroom improvement, and water quality. China and the partnering governments should formalize SESAs and view it as a crucial step that enhances the project. In sum, this study suggests China can take more clearly specific actions for managing the environmental impacts. It is also crucial for Vietnam to understand SESAs and EIAs to negotiate with China to clarify the loans' conditions and ask for adding better environmental protection terms before signing the contracts.

Searching back in the 1990s, China and some of its bordering countries (e.g., Russia, Mongolia) signed bilateral policies for collaboration on ecological issues and environmental protection (Zhang, 2017), many policies on deforestation and strategies to reduce carbon emissions through afforestation along with parts of the road. Through these efforts, there is a great prospect to minimize biodiversity loss along large portions of the proposed route of BRI (Hughes, 2019). Therefore, Vietnam should negotiate to sign the same environmental and resource protection policies with China before joining the BRI.

China has currently released some new messages and some adjustments that were meant to address environmental issues. It is the commitment to build a "green road" and "a pure silk road" that drives BRI towards high quality and environmentally friendly projects. This step creates the right Chinese image and reputation in Vietnam and other nations. According to Professor Wang from the University of New South Wales, a highly structured institutional and regulatory plan on environmental issues can foster trust in host communities and minimize project risk. He also added

that older agreements might not prove compatible with newer initiatives without an overarching framework. With the large-scale cross-border corridor projects, it is advisable to harmonize the standards, procedures, and safety when the projects are operational officially (Belt & Road News, 2019). This study suggests China make more efforts to implement these essential ideas.

4.4 Financial policies

For China, financial policies will offer a practical way to activate higher-level policies since many financial organizations implement sustainability policies. These financial policies should be obeyed and included compulsory EIAs, reducing plan development's potential impacts. Government, financial banks, and BRI beneficiary countries establish and conduct worldwide environmental protection in their loan lending and borrowing. If an additional 5 percent of the funds can create any project green, the investment transaction should be made toward greening directions (Yang & Yang, 2019).

To reduce economic dependence on China, Vietnam should diversify loan channels into high-quality infrastructure. Apart from traditional partners, such as ADB or World Bank, Vietnam should pay attention to the lending programs that Japan is promoting through Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) and Japan Bank for International Cooperation (JBIC). Simultaneously, Vietnam can link more strongly and closely with other countries, with non-China free trade agreements (FTAs) that will create a more balanced position and avoid getting caught in the BRI orbit. Moreover, Vietnam can still keep its eyes on the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP), ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), and European Union (EU) engagement, which will be safer. Ensuring a development balance between BRI and TPP/EU/AEC might enable Vietnam to benefit from those aids. All these policies will ultimately increase Vietnam's trade and investment development in response to be not profoundly dependent on China's economy and loans.

4.5 Balancing policies

First, Vietnam can continue its domestic reforms to promote the development and improve national capacity, especially in prioritized areas such as maritime security and the fishing industry. Actions the country can take to achieve these goals include developing its coast guard, raising maritime domain awareness, and modernizing its fishing fleet. To do this can contribute to a new, dynamic strategic balance of power in the region (Thai, 2018).

Second, Vietnam will be consistent in its balancing policies in relations with regional countries (e.g., Asian countries) and major powers (e.g., China, the USA). Vietnam can negotiate with Asian regional economies in order to keep a balanced pathway to make sure peaceful, stable, and developmental in the region along with respecting the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC), the Bali Concord I and II, the ASEAN Charter, the Treaty on the Southeast Asian Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone.

Especially after the 12th National Congress of the Chinese Communist Party, balancing diplomatic measures between China and the United States was considered significant leverage. Vietnam's bargaining power will be increased if Vietnam takes advantage of leverage to improve its relationship with the USA and China for its economic and security interests.

Additionally, on the maritime issue, Vietnam can call for strict implementation of the shared understandings and agreements on fundamental principles guiding the settlement of sea-related problems. At the same time, Vietnam should follow the Declaration on the Conduct (DOC) of Parties in the South China Sea fully and effectively and actively negotiate to build a substantive and practical Code of Conduct (COC) in the South China Sea. These agreements will help manage disputes and prevent external forces' use or threat and provide essential principles guiding the behavior and relations among regional countries outside the region to maintain peace and stability.

5. Conclusion

This study's central concentration is to understand better the risk impact of Vietnam-China cooperation and how to minimize these risks to pave the way for Vietnam to join the BRI officially. Our findings provide significant implications for learners and practitioners. First, our study enhances the BRI's academic knowledge and its implementation through the five key "connectivities," focusing on this Asian country (Vietnam). Second, the study is informative for local people in showing how BRI impacts many international industries, such as education, tourism, trading, and foreign investment flows. From this, local enterprises can actively adapt their business plans for future development. Third, we hope that

policymakers will have a complete picture of regional geography to mold foreign policies for globalization, sustainable development, and mutual respect for national sovereignty. We conclude that China's outbound interactions with other countries are projected to be more sustainable way.

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